

Research Data Management Workshop for RTG 2297 MathCore¹

“In order to ensure the success of our doctoral students they participate in a tailored structured study program. It contains training units in form of compact courses and weekly seminars, encouraging early integration into the scientific community and networking.”

[MathCoRe - Mathematical Complexity Reduction - OVGU](#)

MathCoRe stands for Mathematical Complexity Reduction - a Research Training Group (RTG) located at Otto-von-Guericke-Universität Magdeburg ([OVGU](#)). The RTG is a Graduiertenkolleg ([DFG-GRK 2297](#)) funded by [Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft \(DFG\)](#). Headed by the Faculty of Mathematics ([FMA](#)) it is run as a cooperation with the Faculty of Electrical Engineering and Information Technology ([FEIT](#)) and the Max Planck Institute for the Dynamics of Complex Technical Systems([MPI](#))

List of research projects: [Projects - Mathematical Complexity Reduction - OVGU](#)

Publications: https://www.mathcore.ovgu.de/index.php?show=research_publications

Monday, 23.01.2023 (10:00 a.m. until 5:00 p.m) - RDM introduction

Guest lecturer: Dr. Torsten Rathmann, Bergische Universität Wuppertal²

OVGU Campus (G9 - 211), siehe Campusplan:

[Campusplan+Uni+Magdeburg.pdf \(ovgu.de\)](#)

Program:

10:00 -10:15 - Welcome (Annette Strauch-Davey (ASD), M.A., **FDM@OVGU** Central Coordination and Data Stewardship Coordinator)

10:15 - 11:00 - Basics (Dr. Torsten Rathmann (TR), Research Data Management Bergische Universität Wuppertal)

11:00 -11:15 - Introduction of participants and RDM support (Jun.-Prof. Jan Heiland and ALL) and coffee / tea / biscuits

11:15 - 12:00 - RDM Services@OVGU (in a common strategy for all and together, Data Stewardship & what's in it for "maths" , ASD)

12:00 - 1:00 - Free licences for research data (TR)

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https://www.dfg.de/gefoerderte_projekte/programme_und_projekte/listen/projektetails/index.jsp?id=314838170&sort=nr_asc&prg=GRK®ion=15&wb=3&prgvar= (Accessed on 27th Nov. 2022)

² <https://fdm.uni-wuppertal.de/de/support/unser-team/ansicht/rathmann/>
(Accessed on 27th Nov. 2022)

1:00 - 1:45 Lunch (sandwiches and other delights)

1:45 - 3:00 Different types research data storage and accessibility in the sense of FAIR data (ASD)

3:00 - 4:00 Data Management Plan (TR)

4:00 - 5:00 Discussions according to the participants' needs in MathCore (requirements, support from OVGU and the mathematical RDM-community)

5:00 - Send-off (workshop over - and keeping in touch)

NFDI - cooperations, e.g.

MaRDI

Building a community that embraces a FAIR data culture and research workflow through the sustainable realization of MaRDI findings.

[Mission - MaRDI \(mardi4nfdi.de\)](http://mardi4nfdi.de)

Mathematical research data is vast, complex and multifaceted. It emerges within mathematical sciences but also in other scientific areas such as physics, chemistry, life sciences and the Arts. Standardised formats, data interoperability and application programming interfaces need to be developed to ensure the ease of use of data across broad disciplines.

With this in mind, the Mathematical Research Data Initiative (MaRDI) is being established as the consortia initiative of mathematical science. Its mission is to:

1. develop a robust Mathematical Research Data Infrastructure that would be useful within mathematics and other disciplines as well as non-scientific fields.
2. set standards and confirmable workflows for certified Mathematical Research Data and
3. provide services to both the mathematical and wider scientific community.

**Further questions: Annette Strauch-Davey, M.A.,
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